

Research Paper

A market-based approach to assessing the capacity value of variable renewable energy: Evidence from the Dominican Republic

René Báez-Santana ^{a,*} ,
 Víctor Ocaña-Guevara ^{a,c} ,
 Luis Hernández-Callejo ^f

^a Área de Ciencias Básicas, Instituto Tecnológico de Santo Domingo, 49 Los Próceres Avenue, Santo Domingo 10602, Dominican Republic

^b Área de Ingeniería, Instituto Tecnológico de Santo Domingo, 49 Los Próceres Avenue, Santo Domingo 10602, Dominican Republic

^c Facultad de Ingeniería Mecánica e Industrial, Universidad Central "Marta Abreu" de Las Villas (UCLV), Santa Clara, Cuba

^d Electrical Energy Department, Universidade Federal de Juiz de Fora (UFJF), Minas Gerais, Brazil

^e GECAD - Research Group on Intelligent Engineering and Computing for Advanced Innovation and Development, LASI - Intelligent Systems Associate Laboratory, ISEP, Polytechnic of Porto, Portugal

^f Departamento Ingeniería Agrícola y Forestal, Universidad de Valladolid, Soria 42004, Spain

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ABSTRACT

The growing integration of variable renewable energy (VRE) challenges traditional capacity valuation methods in electricity markets, which mainly rely on probabilistic models and technical adequacy metrics and are not linked to market design and economic incentives. This study introduces a new approach to assessing the Economic Capacity Value (ECV) of VRE resources, which measures their contribution to system reliability, considering resource availability and market conditions. The methodology is applied using a co-optimization model of the energy market and the capacity remuneration mechanism that minimizes total system costs and capacity payments. The framework is applied to the Dominican Republic's electricity market, using 2023 demand and generation data. Results show that VRE resources provide a significant contribution to system reliability under existing market conditions. Solar photovoltaic ECVs range from 21.8 MW (17.2%) in the north region to 107.2 MW (33.6%) in the southwest, while wind power exhibits higher values, reaching 87.6 MW (43.9%) in the north and 74.7 MW (34.4%) in the southwest. In all cases, ECV surpasses the capacity factor, indicating that VRE contributes more to reliability than its average production suggests. Sensitivity analysis shows that ECV is highly sensitive to market design parameters, with $\pm 25\%$ variations in capacity payments or scarcity prices resulting in ECV changes of up to 34%. These findings show that capacity value can be influenced by both resource availability during high demand periods and market design, supporting the inclusion of VRE in capacity remuneration mechanisms based on ECV.

1. Introduction

Electricity markets need continued regulatory adaptation to support the transition toward low-carbon power systems. This requirement is especially significant with the growing share of solar and wind power, known collectively as variable renewable energy (VRE), along with emerging technologies. Integrating VRE generally requires new market mechanisms and reliability measures to properly reflect its operational features and contributions to the system (Brito-Pereira et al., 2022).

Globally, the rapid expansion of VRE has helped decrease greenhouse gas emissions and wholesale electricity prices (Executive summary, 2024). Nevertheless, it has also changed the generation mix and introduced new operational conditions, particularly with respect to system reliability.

These changes highlight the importance of thoroughly evaluating the performance of wind and solar power within electricity markets, especially as they coexist with complementary resources like demand response and energy storage (Richardson and Harvey, 2015). Each resource contributes differently to meeting system demand, particularly

* Corresponding author.

E-mail addresses: rene.baezs@intec.edu.do, renebaez@gmail.com (R. Báez-Santana), miguel.aybar@intec.edu.do (M. Aybar-Mejía), maximo.dominguez@intec.edu.do (M. Domínguez-Garabitos), victor.ocana@intec.edu.do (V. Ocaña-Guevara), bruno.dias@uff.br (B. Henriques-Dias), jan@isep.ipp.pt (J. Soares), luis.hernandez.callejo@uva.es (L. Hernández-Callejo).

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Table 1
Capacity valuation - comparison of international experiences.

Market	Mechanism	De-rating	Method	Period of calculation	Ref.
Chile	Capacity payment	Capacity factor	Initial firm capacity is calculated with the capacity factor, and afterwards, a probabilistic process (convolution) calculates the firm capacity to be remunerated.	Five years or 52 peak hours in the last year (depending on which of the two capacity factors results in lower).	(Galetovic et al., 2015)
Peru	Capacity payment	Capacity factor	Average production	Peak-demand hours of the last three years.	(Rudnick and Velasquez, 2019; COES, 2019, 2020)
PJM	Centralized auction	Capacity factor	Average production	Summer Peak-demand hours of the last three years.	(PJM, 2025)
MISO	Centralized auction	Capacity value/Capacity factor	Wind - ELCC of the total wind capacity, distributed by the total production	Eight yearly peak-demand hours in the last eleven summer periods.	(MISO, 2025)
		Capacity factor	Solar - average production	Summer Peak-demand hours of the last three years.	
CAISO	Decentralized auction	Capacity value/capacity factor	ELCC plus a diversity adjustment	Projected data for one month.	(California Public Utilities Commission, 2020; B. and Hobbs, 2017)

by design, largely unaffected by current electricity market conditions.

Simultaneously, a considerable body of literature demonstrates that regulatory design and market mechanisms greatly impact system reliability. Capacity payments interact with wholesale market price caps to mitigate the “missing money” problem, where suppressed scarcity prices prevent generators from recovering fixed costs, thus supporting resource adequacy (Joskow, 2008; Milstein and Tishler, 2019). Other studies show that both scarcity pricing and capacity remuneration mechanisms can improve capacity adequacy (Petitet et al., 2017), while broader theoretical frameworks explicitly link price caps, scarcity pricing, and capacity remuneration to generator availability and system reliability (Bublitz et al., 2019).

Despite these insights, to the authors’ knowledge, no existing framework explicitly quantifies the combined effect of market conditions and resource availability on reliability in terms of capacity value. Existing approaches do not capture how scarcity pricing, capacity payments, and market design features jointly influence the effective capacity contribution of VRE resources. This gap highlights the need for methodologies that incorporate market conditions into capacity value assessments.

1.2. Contributions of this work

This work introduces a novel method to estimate the Economic Capacity Value (ECV) of VRE power plants. The ECV combines resource availability during periods of high demand or scarcity with current market conditions to measure a resource’s contribution to system reliability in economic terms. In this context, the ECV is defined as the effective capacity contribution of a generating resource, influenced both by its physical availability and the current market design. It is crucial to distinguish the ECV from traditional reliability metrics, such as the ELCC or the Firm Capacity Equivalent (FCE), which assess technical reliability but do not reflect how market conditions or market design could affect their contribution to reliability.

The Dominican Republic’s wholesale electricity market serves as a case study. Utility-scale renewable generation in the country has grown rapidly, rising from 14 GWh in 2011–2237 GWh in 2023 (2023 annual report - Organismo Coordinador), with continued growth expected. To ensure security of supply, the Dominican Republic employs a CRM that compensates thermal and hydropower generation, while VRE has been supported through separate fiscal incentive schemes (Regulation for the Application of the Law 57–07 of incentives for the development of renewable energy sources and their special regimes). These incentives, however, have been subject to regulatory adjustment, most notably their reduction in 2012, reflecting the vulnerability of these kinds of support mechanisms to government policy changes (Battie et al., 2012). To attract investment, the state may sign PPAs with VRE projects,

potentially resulting in costly projects and consequently high energy prices, while bearing most of the risk.

The current separation between the CRM and renewable support schemes misses the chance to include VRE into the CRM. The proposed framework can deal with this matter by integrating VRE into the existing CRM. As a wholesale market mechanism, the risk of policy changes driven by government priorities is mitigated, thereby enhancing regulatory stability and investment effectiveness.

The rest of the paper is organized as follows. 2 explains the materials and methods, including data sources, modeling, and the methodology used to estimate the ECV of VRE resources. 3 shows and discusses the results of the case study. 4 concludes the paper by highlighting the key findings and suggesting directions for future research.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Data collection

This work uses a dataset for an optimization model of the Dominican Republic’s generation mix and system demand in 2023. The data includes an open-access database of institutions and utilities in the country’s power sector, as well as websites and databases from international organizations.

Power generation and variable cost data were obtained from the Dominican Republic’s Independent System Operator (Organismo Coordinador, OC) and complemented with publicly available information from the regulatory entity (Superintendencia de Electricidad, SIE), the policymaker (Comisión Nacional de Energía, CNE), and the North American Electric Reliability Corporation (NERC). All sources are official and publicly accessible, ensuring transparency and replicability.

Datasets were consolidated into a single raw data repository and processed with Python (pandas and datetime). A more detailed explanation of the dataset can be found in the data article (Báez-Santana et al., 2025), for transparency. The dataset is also accessible through a data repository (see Data availability in this work). The following subsections provide a brief overview of the data.

2.1.1. Economic parameters

In the Dominican Republic, the capacity payment price is determined by the regulatory authority and compensates the firm capacity provided by conventional generation units. This regulated price is based on the investment and fixed operating costs of a reference open-cycle gas turbine with 50 MW of installed capacity, adjusted by an applicable derating factor.

In addition to capacity remuneration, the regulatory authority sets an annual scarcity price and/or price cap (PC), which is adjusted monthly through an indexation mechanism. The methodology to

determine the scarcity price applied by the regulatory entity is a subject of debate, in the sense that it does not reflect the actual value of scarcity. Consequently, short-term price signals in the energy market can become distorted since the administratively set scarcity price is not fully aligned with the reliability level expected by consumers. This misalignment can hinder efficient generation expansion and investment decisions. According to the OC, there have been cases where peaking units with variable costs exceeding the scarcity price have declared indefinite unavailability, thus reducing their firm capacity and negatively impacting system reliability. Similar issues have happened in other countries, e.g., Colombia (Llanos Pérez and Olascuaga, 2016).

In the Dominican Republic’s electricity market, variable costs include both fuel-related and non-fuel components. For this study, the variable costs of thermal generators are classified by technology type and primary energy source. These data are published daily by the OC in the day-ahead market reports and are consistently used across all operating periods each day.

Table 2 summarizes these economic parameters, explaining their units of measurement and the frequency at which they are defined or updated. The table emphasizes the different time scales of long-term investment signals, such as capacity payments, compared to short-term operational signals, including scarcity pricing and variable costs.

2.1.2. Technical parameters

The total capacity of conventional generation units was categorized by technology and primary energy sources, while the total capacity of non-conventional renewable units was categorized by technology (wind and solar) and geographical location (north, southeast, and southwest). For this model, Table 3 presents the net effective power (or installed capacity) of power plants in the Dominican Republic, sorted by technology and primary energy source. This classification covers conventional thermal power plants (steam turbines, combined cycle gas turbines, internal combustion engines, and gas turbines) as well as renewable energy sources (solar photovoltaics and wind turbines). The data offers a complete overview of the energy mix within the system, forming the basis for the capacity payment analysis discussed in this study.

To understand how the VRE mix is distributed among regions according to the data, Fig. 1 presents the installed capacity (or net effective power) of VRE by location and region. Solar PV is present in all regions; however, wind power plants are located only in the north and southwest regions.

The forced outage rate (FOR) quantifies the reliability and performance of power units such as turbines and engines. It indicates the percentage of time a power plant is unexpectedly unavailable due to failure or other unplanned issues. The availability factor (AF) measures the proportion of time a generating unit or system is available to produce power when required, excluding periods when it is out of service for scheduled maintenance. The values considered for both parameters are presented in Table 4:

2.1.3. Hourly data

The dataset includes hourly observations that capture the physical, operational, and economic features of the power system with adequate time resolution. Dates are recorded in the YYYY-MM-DD format, the Day

Table 2
Economic parameters characteristics.

Economic parameter	Unit	Periodicity	Value
Capacity Payment	USD/ MW-year	Yearly	119,774.28
Price cap/ Scarcity price	USD/ MWh	Monthly	Available in the data repository (in an hourly format)
Variable costs	USD/ MWh	Daily	

Table 3

Net effective power of power plants by technology and primary energy source.

Technology/Location	Primary energy source	Code	Net effective power [MW]
STEAM TURBINE	BIOMASS	STTUBIOM	27.8
STEAM TURBINE	COAL	STTUCOAL	957.3
CCGT	NATURAL GAS	CCGTNGAS	762.1
CCGT	GAS AND FUEL OIL #2	CCGTGFO2	259.8
INTERNAL COMBUSTION ENGINE	GAS AND FUEL OIL #6	ICENGF06	504.0
INTERNAL COMBUSTION ENGINE	FUEL OIL #6	ICOENF06	498.7
GAS TURBINE	NATURAL GAS	GASTNGAS	63.4
GAS TURBINE	FUEL OIL #2	GASTUFO2	99.8
SOLAR-PV-NORTH	SUN	SOLPVNOR	126.6
SOLAR-PV-SOUTHEAST	SUN	SOLPVSEA	179.9
SOLAR-PV-SOUTHWEST	SUN	SOLPVSWE	318.6
WIND-TURBINE-NORTH	WIND	WINDTNOR	199.8
WIND-TURBINE-SOUTHWEST	WIND	WINDTSWE	217.3

column shows the day of the month, the Period column refers to the periods in a day, and the Yearly Period column specifies the period within the year.

At the hourly level, the dataset includes electricity generation data from commercial metering of VRE power plants, disaggregated by geographic region. Additionally, hourly system demand is derived by aggregating commercial metering data from all power plants connected to the system, thereby embedding transmission losses in the demand values. Hourly data for 2023 (8760 h) were obtained from the OC.

To better evaluate how different generation technologies contribute to meeting system demand, the concept of residual demand is used. Residual demand is defined as the part of total demand remaining after subtracting generation from VRE and non-commercial units. This metric provides insight into the extent to which VRE and non-commercial generation reduce hourly demand, particularly during peak periods.

Building on this definition, a final vector is created by calculating the difference between total system demand and the sum of outputs from non-commercial and hydroelectric generation (also available in the data repository). This vector represents the hourly energy that must be supplied by commercially available thermal power plants (defined as units eligible for dispatch by the OC) along with VRE generation. This series is then used as the demand input for the optimization model.

Table 5 summarizes the main hourly data variables used in this study, detailing their units of measurement, data sources, and availability. All variables are derived from commercial metering data, ensuring a consistent representation of system operations. The table distinguishes between observed quantities, such as total system demand and VRE generation, and constructed variables, including residual demand and the demand input used in the model.

2.2. Model

A simple deterministic mathematical model that combines the energy market and the capacity payment was developed. The model is adapted to the GAMS modelling language and optimizes a cost-minimization function using the CPLEX solver, subject to basic constraints.

2.2.1. Objective function and constraints

The objective function in Eq. (1) minimizes the total cost (\$) of energy production, capacity payments, and non-served energy. The capacity payments are determined by the product of the capacity payment

Fig. 1. Installed capacity of VRE by location and region in the Dominican Republic at the end of 2023.

Table 4
FOR and AF of thermal power plants.

Technology	Primary energy source	Code	FOR	AF
STEAM TURBINE	BIOMASS	STTUBIOM	12.41%	75.01%
STEAM TURBINE	COAL	STTUOCOAL	12.41%	75.01%
CCGT	NATURAL GAS	CCGTNGAS	6.24%	84.89%
CCGT	GAS AND FUEL OIL #2	CCGTGFO2	6.24%	84.89%
INTERNAL COMBUSTION ENGINE	GAS AND FUEL OIL #6	ICENGFO6	12.07%	92.19%
INTERNAL COMBUSTION ENGINE	FUEL OIL #6	ICOENFO6	12.07%	92.19%
GAS TURBINE	NATURAL GAS	GASTNGAS	33.76%	87.82%
GAS TURBINE	FUEL OIL #2	GASTUFO2	33.76%	87.82%

Table 5
Hourly data characteristics.

Data	Unit	Source	Value
VRE generation	MWh	Commercial metering	Available in the data repository
Total demand	MWh	Commercial metering	Available in the data repository
Residual demand	MWh	Commercial metering (Total demand minus VRE generation)	
Demand input for the model	MWh	Commercial metering (Total demand minus noncommercial generation minus hydro generation)	

price (CMP) and the firm capacity fc_g of each generating unit g . The generation cost is calculated by multiplying the variable cost $VC_{p,g}$ and the corresponding dispatched energy $ep_{p,g}$. Lastly, the non-served energy (NSENE) cost, represented by the product of the price cap/scarcity price PC_p and the amount of non-served energy nse_p .

$$\text{MIN Cost} = \sum_g [\text{CMP} * fc_g] + \sum_{p,g} [VC_{p,g} * ep_{p,g}] + \sum_p [PC_p * nse_p] \quad (1)$$

This formulation allows the model to co-optimize energy dispatch, capacity remuneration, and load shedding during scarcity conditions. While including nonlinear cost or efficiency functions would improve

the model, it is not necessary to demonstrate how market conditions impact reliability, as measured by the ECV. Additionally, the case study assumes production costs are linear, aligning with the regulatory framework of the Dominican Republic electricity market. Under current regulation, the OC calculates a single variable cost for generators that applies uniformly across all production levels (Organismo Coordinador, 2023a), and this price is used for market clearing and settlement. Therefore, the model's linear cost representations align with both the regulatory framework and the available market data, as documented in the associated data repository.

Total electricity supply, including dispatched generation and any non-served energy, must equal the system demand D_p in each period. Eq. (2) enforces a system-wide power balance in each period:

$$\sum_g [ep_{p,g}] + nse_p = D_p; \forall p \quad (2)$$

To ensure that the maximum dispatchable energy of thermal unit t reflects its effective availability after accounting for its forced outage rate, Eq. (3) limits the dispatched energy of thermal units by their available firm capacity adjusted for forced outage rates FOR_t :

$$ep_{p,t} \leq fc_t * (1 - FOR_t); \forall p, t \quad (3)$$

Solar and wind generation are considered non-dispatchable and are equal to the solar and wind power outputs recorded by commercial metering in a region. Eqs. (4) and (5) set the energy production of solar photovoltaic and wind turbine units to their respective generation profiles:

$$ep_{p,s} = SPV_{p,s}; \forall p, s \quad (4)$$

$$ep_{p,w} = WTU_{p,w}; \forall p, w \quad (5)$$

To account for maintenance, Eq. (6) constrains the total energy production from thermal power plants to their accredited firm capacity adjusted by an availability factor because AF_t and the duration H (the number of hours in the year), ensuring consistency between capacity availability and feasible energy delivery.

$$\sum_p ep_{p,t} \leq fc_t * AF_t * H; \forall t \quad (6)$$

To ensure an upward spinning reserve ROD_p in each period, Eq. (7) guarantees that sufficient unused firm capacity remains available to meet the reserve obligation, thereby supporting system reliability under

uncertainty and peak conditions. The current Dominican regulation requires that this reserve margin be between 3% and 5% of the demand in each period (Regulation for the Application of the General Electricity Law 125-01, 2012). For this work, a 5% margin was considered.

$$\sum_t [fc_t - ep_{p,t}] \geq ROD_p; \forall p \tag{7}$$

Together, Eqs. (1) – (7) establish a co-optimized energy market and capacity remuneration mechanism model that determines generation

Fig. 2. Flow chart of the methodology.

dispatch, capacity payments, and non-served energy valuation subject to operational constraints and reliability standards.

2.2.2. Model context and assumptions

The proposed model adopts a market and system-level approach used within a methodology to measure the contribution of VRE resources to overall system reliability under market conditions. Although advanced planning and operational optimization models in transmission and generation expansion (A generation and transmission, 2024; Generation and transmission, 2025), or models commonly applied to microgrids (Halidou et al., 2026; Tahirou Halidou et al., 2023), and distribution networks (A bi-level optimization approach, 2025), can be adapted, the present formulation focuses on a market-based reliability valuation rather than operational decision-making. This modeling choice is intentional, as this study aims to develop a transparent and reproducible capacity valuation methodology consistent with centralized market and regulatory settings, more aligned with policymakers. Advanced optimization-based frameworks are ideal for sizing, dispatch, and complex energy management problems more oriented to system operators and planners.

Solar and wind generation are represented using historical hourly production profiles for the year 2023 obtained from the OC; according to the system operator (Organismo Coordinador, 2023b), utility-scale VRE curtailment was not implemented or formally recorded during this period; systematic curtailment events began only in 2025, so the observed production data accurately represent delivered energy without requiring an explicit curtailment decision variable.

Hourly data for the year in question is used. In (Hasche et al., 2011), the results show that at least four to five years of wind data at hourly resolution are necessary for reliable studies, in the case of wind. In (Madaeni et al., 2013), several approaches that use hourly solar generation to estimate solar capacity value are compared. This study indicates that multiple years of data are required for robust estimation of the capacity value. However, for this mechanism, the capacity value (ECV) of VRE to be determined is based on the annual contribution of these technologies to system reliability, justifying a payment for that year's contribution since it calculates the ECV retroactively (ex-post).

2.3. Process

The model is applied in two stages, as illustrated in Fig. 2. The first stage is described in subsection 2.3.1, while the second stage is detailed in subsections 2.3.2 and 2.3.3.

2.3.1. First stage

In the first stage, a base case is established to describe the current market and system conditions. The firm capacity of conventional thermal generation is limited by the net effective power declared by each unit, while the annual energy output of renewable generation is fully considered.

This stage evaluates how the current price cap or scarcity price impacts both the firm capacity and energy production of thermal generators, with energy production explicitly limited by declared firm capacity. When capacity payments and revenues during scarcity hours are insufficient to recover fixed and variable costs, generators may decrease availability or exit the market, resulting in reduced energy output and lower firm capacity due to weakened economic incentives (Bonaldo et al., 2024; Liu et al., 2021).

The optimization yields an estimate of thermal generation, firm capacity, and the resulting NSENE. The latter is then used as the reference system reliability level for the analysis.

2.3.2. Second stage

In the second stage, the generation of a specific VRE technology–location group is removed from the system, and an additional reliability constraint is added to the optimization model. Eq. (8) sets the

upper limit of non-served energy to the amount obtained in the base case. An upper bound is set, rather than enforcing equality, to prevent unrealistic results where the model intentionally sheds load to match the base-case non-served energy even if generation costs are low. This formulation defines a maximum acceptable reliability shortfall without artificially forcing demand curtailment.

$$\sum_p nse_p \leq NSENE_{Base\ Case} \quad (8)$$

Removing VRE generation increases the required firm capacity of conventional thermal units to satisfy the reliability constraint. This incremental firm capacity requirement is interpreted as the equivalent firm capacity contribution of the removed VRE resource, which becomes the initial ECV. The process is repeated for each VRE technology–location group to determine its initial ECV.

2.3.3. Scarcity price uplift and definitive ECV

An additional outcome of the second stage is estimating a scarcity price uplift, which occurs only when the reliability constraint in Eq. (8) is binding. In this case, the dual variable associated with the non-served energy constraint is given by Eq. (9):

$$\lambda_{NSENE} = \frac{\delta OF^*}{\delta NSENE} \quad (9)$$

Where λ_{NSENE} represents the marginal reduction in total system cost (δOF^*) resulting from a marginal increase of 1 MWh in allowable non-served energy ($\delta NSENE$). Consequently, during periods of scarcity, the actual marginal cost of energy equals the current scarcity price plus the corresponding uplift (λ_{NSENE}). This uplift offers an additional economic signal that complements the increase in firm capacity identified in the second stage by quantifying the impact of removing VRE generation on the scarcity price.

To refine the ECV estimation, the energy generated by each VRE technology–location group during scarcity periods is monetized using the respective scarcity price uplift. This total value is then divided by the annualized capacity payment to determine an incremental ECV.

$$\Delta ECV_l = \frac{\lambda_{NSENE,l} * \sum_p GS_{p,l}}{CMP} \quad (10)$$

Where:

ΔECV_l : Additional economic capacity value for Technology-Location group l [MW].

$\lambda_{NSENE,l}$: Scarcity price uplift for Technology-Location group l [USD/MWh].

$GS_{p,l}$: Generation during scarcity of Technology-Location group l in period p [MWh].

CMP : Annualized capacity payment price [USD/MW-Year].

The definitive ECV of Technology-Location group l is therefore obtained as:

$$Definitive\ ECV_l = Initial\ ECV_l + \Delta ECV_l \quad (11)$$

2.3.4. Capacity payments allocation

A practical challenge concerns the allocation of capacity payments among multiple VRE power plants of the same technology within a given region. The proposed mechanism addresses this issue by distributing the ECV in proportion to each plant's contribution to energy generation during scarcity periods. Under this approach, the ECV attributed to individual solar PV and wind power plants within a region depends directly on their relative energy production during scarcity conditions.

$$ECV_{g \in l} = \frac{ES_g}{\sum_g ES_g} * ECV_l \quad (12)$$

Eq. (12) shows how the ECV attributed to plant g is calculated. The

energy share of each VRE plant g , denoted by ES_g is computed as its contribution to the total energy generated by all plants in the same technology–location group during scarcity hours.

2.4. Scenario design for sensitivity analysis

A sensitivity analysis was designed to evaluate the robustness of the proposed ECV methodology with respect to uncertainty in key market design parameters. The analysis focuses on two parameters that directly influence investment incentives and scarcity signals in the wholesale electricity market: (a) the capacity payment price (CMP) defined within the capacity remuneration mechanism, and (b) the scarcity price or price cap (PC) used in the energy market during scarcity conditions. Four alternative scenarios were developed by applying $\pm 25\%$ variations to each parameter while keeping all other model inputs constant.

In the first set of scenarios, the CMP was varied by 25% both upward and downward from the base case. These scenarios aim to assess how changes in the remuneration level for firm capacity affect the amount of committed conventional capacity in the base case and, consequently, the additional firm capacity required when VRE generation is withdrawn. The resulting changes in ECV indicate the sensitivity of VRE ECV to the capacity payment price.

In the second set of scenarios, the PC was increased and decreased by 25%. These scenarios are designed to analyze the effect of scarcity pricing on the allocation of firm capacity and on the additional ECV gained from scarcity price uplifts, as defined in the proposed methodology. These scenarios assess how a tighter or looser PC influences the market's ability to signal scarcity and support capacity adequacy.

For each scenario, the process described in 2.3 was repeated, including the base case optimization and the second-stage calculation of additional firm capacity following the withdrawal of VRE generation. The resulting ECV values were then compared across scenarios to evaluate the methodology's sensitivity to variations in market design parameters.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. First stage: base case scenario

Table 6 reports the firm capacity of thermal generation technologies in the base case. While CCGT units and coal-fired steam turbines retain firm capacities equal to their net effective power, open-cycle turbines and internal combustion technologies exhibit markedly lower firm capacity contributions. In particular, the GASTUFO2 and GASTNGAS units are assigned zero firm capacity, whereas ICOENFO6 retains only 60.1 MW, corresponding to 12.1% of its effective net capacity. Under this configuration, the model yields a total non-served energy of 467,477 MWh, which is set as the target reliability level for the second stage of the methodology.

Table 6 highlights the interaction between market parameters and operational availability in determining firm capacity in the base case. Technologies assigned zero or very low firm capacity can be interpreted as those for which capacity payments and scarcity-hour revenues are

Table 6

Firm capacity of thermal generation: Base case.

Technology code	Net effective power [MW]	Firm capacity [MW]
CCGTGFO2	259.8	259.8
CCGTNGAS	762.1	762.1
GASTUFO2	99.8	0.0
GASTNGAS	63.4	0.0
ICOENFO6	498.7	60.1
ICENGFO6	504.0	504.0
STTUBIOM	27.8	27.8
STTUCCOAL	957.3	957.3
Total	3172.9	2571.1

insufficient to recover fixed and variable costs, leading to their unavailability in the optimization model. This situation exhibits how an inadequate scarcity price and capacity payment can weaken the contribution of peaking and flexible thermal units to system reliability. As a result, the decrease in firm capacity relative to the effective net power influences the NSENE level, which is used as the reliability benchmark in the second stage. This connects market design parameters with both reliability outcomes and the capacity value of VRE.

3.2. Second stage: estimating additional thermal firm capacity

In the second stage of the methodology, VRE generation for a specific technology–location group is removed, and a constraint is added to limit non-served energy to the base case reliability level (NSENE). The deterministic formulation reflects the operational and market design features (e.g., scarcity price and capacity payments) of the Dominican Republic's electricity market. In this context, NSENE provides a clear, economically relevant indicator of reliability, as it captures scarcity conditions that directly influence market signals.

Under these conditions and considering that hourly generation from thermal units is limited by their firm capacity, the model automatically assigns additional firm capacity to conventional generation to ensure a certain level of system reliability. For the case of Solar PV located in the northern region (SOLPVNOR), this results in a 21.8 MW increase in the firm capacity of conventional thermal generation. Table 7 presents the firm capacity results after excluding SOLPVNOR generation. The increase in firm capacity is attributable to the ICOENFO6 technology, which increases from 60.1 MW in the base case to 81.9 MW. All other thermal technologies remain unchanged relative to the base case. The resulting increment of 21.8 MW represents the equivalent firm capacity required to replace the reliability contribution of SOLPVNOR and therefore constitutes its ECV.

For 2023, the resulting ECV for SOLPVNOR is 21.8 MW. Relative to an installed solar PV capacity of 126.6 MW in the northern region, this represents 17.2% of effective net capacity. The same process is then applied to all remaining VRE technology–location pairs to calculate their respective ECV. Table 8 summarizes the ECV results across all VRE technologies and regions. The ECV [%] column expresses the ECV as a share of the net effective power (or installed capacity), enabling direct comparison across technologies and locations.

Fig. 3 further compares the calculated ECV values with the corresponding capacity factors for 2023. This comparison emphasizes the conceptual difference between energy-based and reliability-based performance metrics. The capacity factor reflects average energy production relative to the installed capacity, while the ECV measures each resource's contribution to system adequacy under current market conditions. The ECVs are also divided by the installed capacity and shown as percentages to facilitate comparison with the capacity factor.

Across all technologies and regions, the ECV exceeds the capacity factor. This shows that, under the market conditions seen in 2023, VRE technologies contribute more to system reliability than what their

Table 7

Conventional thermal generation firm capacity: SOLPVNOR.

Technology/ Location	Firm capacity: Base Case [MW] (A)	Firm capacity: SOLPVNOR [MW] (B)	Difference [MW] (B) - (A)
CCGTGFO2	259.8	259.8	0.0
CCGTNGAS	762.1	762.1	0.0
GASTUFO2	0.0	0.0	0.0
GASTNGAS	0.0	0.0	0.0
ICOENFO6	60.1	81.9	21.8
ICENGFO6	504.0	504.0	0.0
STTUBIOM	27.8	27.8	0.0
STTUCCOAL	957.3	957.3	0.0
Total	2571.1	2592.9	21.8

Table 8
ECV of VRE generation.

Technology/Location	Code	ECV [MW]	ECV [%]
SOLAR-PV-NORTH	SOLPVNOR	21.8	17.2%
SOLAR-PV-SOUTHEAST	SOLPVSEA	31.5	17.5%
SOLAR-PV-SOUTHWEST	SOLPVSWE	107.2	33.6%
WIND-TURBINE-NORTH	WINDTNOR	87.6	43.9%
WIND-TURBINE-SOUTHWEST	WINDTSWE	74.7	34.4%

average energy production suggests. Thus, both solar PV and wind resources tend to produce electricity during times of high demand or scarcity, even if their yearly generation is relatively modest.

From the perspectives of system planning and resource adequacy, this distinction is significant. ECV assesses how well a resource reduces scarcity risk, rather than its average energy output. Consequently, a technology with a lower capacity factor may still have a higher ECV if its availability coincides with high demand or high risk of scarcity in the system. The results also indicate that wind power plants offer greater reliability contributions than solar PV across regions, and that solar PV installations in the southwest have substantially higher ECVs than those in other areas, highlighting the importance of geographic and temporal alignment in VRE deployment.

The results presented in this study rely on hourly data for system demand and renewable generation collected during a single year (2023). While this method aligns with the ex-post nature of capacity remuneration and scarcity settlement in the Dominican Republic, it is well understood in the literature that ELCC-based capacity valuations can be sensitive to inter-annual variability in demand patterns, weather conditions, and renewable resource availability (Schindler et al., 2022; Kumler et al., 2019). Hence, interannual variability in both system and market conditions is expected to affect the ECV from year to year.

3.2.1. Capacity payments allocation: WINDTNOR

Four wind power plants were operational in the northern region of the Dominican Republic during 2023. Table 9 reports the effective net capacity of each facility, which together totals 199.8 MW.

Scarcity conditions were observed every month in 2023, with scarcity hours ranging from 11.9 h in February to a maximum of 625.3 h in June. (Fig. 4). This temporal variability emphasizes the need to assess

resource contributions during times of high demand and/or scarcity in the system instead of relying on annual averages.

To allocate the regional ECV reported in Table 8 among individual wind power plants, each unit’s share of total energy production during scarcity hours is calculated. For plants $g \in \text{WINDTNOR}$, the ECV is distributed as:

$$ECV_{g \in \text{WINDTNOR}} = \frac{es_g}{\sum_g es_g} * ECV_{\text{WINDTNOR}}$$

Fig. 5 presents the monthly evolution and ranking of ECV for wind power plants in the northern region throughout 2023. The results show that GEN_069 and GEN_072 were the main contributors to system reliability. Interestingly, even though GEN_060 has the same effective net capacity as GEN_069 (52.5 MW), it consistently ranked lower and was sometimes outperformed by GEN_081, which has the smallest installed capacity (46.8 MW). This highlights that installed capacity alone does not fully indicate reliability; availability during shortages is the key factor.

3.3. Sensitivity analysis

A sensitivity analysis was performed to evaluate how uncertainty in input parameters influences the results of the proposed methodology. Four scenarios were simulated to explore how the ECV responds to changes in the capacity payment price (CMP) and the scarcity price or price cap (PC). The analysis is divided into two parts: first, it assesses changes in the capacity payment price (CMP), followed by changes in the scarcity price or price cap (PC).

Table 9
Wind power plants in the north region.

Power plant code	Net effective power [MW]
GEN_060	52.5
GEN_069	52.5
GEN_072	48.0
GEN_081	46.8
	199.8

Fig. 3. ECV and capacity factor of VRE power plants by technology and location in the year 2023.

Fig. 4. Monthly scarcity hours during 2023.

Fig. 5. Wind power plants in the northern region (WINDTNOR) ranked monthly by ECV in 2023.

Fig. 6 presents the results for scenarios in which the CMP was increased and decreased by 25%.

Regarding the capacity payment price (CMP), an increase in this parameter (Scenario: +25% CMP) is expected to decrease the amount of

Fig. 6. /+ 25% CMP scenarios.

firm capacity available for commitment, both in the base case and in ECV calculations for each technology-location group. As a result, this scenario is likely to lead to a lower ECV for most VRE power plants. Compared with the original scenario, the most significant decrease occurs for SOLPVNOR, where the ECV drops from 17.2% to 11.4%, a 5.8 % age-point reduction (33.7%). Conversely, decreasing the CMP (Scenario: –25% CMP) mainly raises ECVs for VRE units, a trend supported by the results, except for SOLPVSE, which diverges from this pattern. Nonetheless, SOLPVSE remains the region where solar PV achieves its highest capacity ECV.

Notably, although an increase in the capacity payment price (CMP) lowers the ECV, the overall income from capacity payments can still be maximized for most VRE power plants. This is because of the interaction between price and quantity in the total revenue formula: Total Capacity Payment = CMP * ECV. Multiplying the CMP by its corresponding ECV for both the base case and the + 25% CMP scenario shows that most VRE units would receive higher total capacity payments under the increased CMP scenario. This suggests that policies aimed at raising the CMP could provide financial benefits not only to conventional generators but also to VRE power plants. Table 10 shows the total capacity payment for 2023 and for the + 25% CMP scenario. In this table, the column Difference [USD] shows the difference between the 2023 capacity payment revenue and the + 25% CMP scenario.

In contrast, the scenario with a 25% reduction in the PC (–25% PC) of the scarcity price or price cap (PC) does not produce consistent economic signals. (Fig. 7). In this scenario, ECV declines across all VRE power plants, with the largest reductions observed at SOLPVNOR and SOLPVSEA. In these cases, the model does not allocate additional firm capacity beyond what is established in the base case, as the reduced PC level is not enough to justify further commitment.

The model estimates a scarcity uplift of 2.325 USD/MWh for SOLPVNOR and 4.875 USD/MWh for SOLPVSEA, with ECVs of just 1.1 MW and 3.2 MW, respectively. This accounts for 0.8% of SOLPVNOR's total installed capacity and 1.8% of SOLPVSEA's total installed capacity. The detailed computation of the definitive ECV for the –25% PC scenario can be seen in Table 11.

This table shows that the largest portion of the definitive ECV comes from the additional ECV calculated based on the scarcity price uplift. As seen in the case of the Dominican Republic, when regulatory authorities set a price cap below the value of lost load (VOLL) or the marginal cost of supply during scarcity conditions, and sometimes even below the variable costs of commercially operating power plants, market participants may be unable to recover their fixed and capital costs. This is especially harmful to peaking units and flexible resources that rely on infrequent but high-revenue scarcity periods. These regulatory constraints contribute to the well-known ‘missing money’ problem, weakening investment incentives and long-term system reliability.

In addition, the Table 11 shows that the + 25% PC scenario produces more consistent results. As PC increases, more conventional thermal firm capacity is committed for the base case; therefore, less additional firm capacity might be needed when VRE generation is withdrawn. Although most VRE power plants experienced a decrease in ECV compared to the original scenario (notably SOLPVSE), WINDTSWE showed a slight increase in ECV. To assess whether this scenario benefits VRE power plants with reduced ECV, it is necessary to calculate the

Table 10
Capacity payments in 2023 vs + 25% CMP scenario.

Code	Capacity payment 2023 [USD]	Capacity payment + 25% CMP [USD]	Difference [USD]
SOLPVNOR	2606,288.38	2157,434.26	(448,854.12)
SOLPVSEA	3775,285.38	3976,506.17	201,220.79
SOLPVSE	12,839,803.07	13,896,811.11	1057,008.04
WINDTNOR	10,497,018.11	10,807,787.90	310,769.79
WINDTSWE	8949,534.38	9421,650.25	472,115.87

additional scarcity revenue resulting from the + 25% PC increase in 2023. This analysis is reserved for future work due to data limitations. However, initial signs suggest that if the additional scarcity income surpasses the income lost from capacity payments, then it is advantageous.

The resulting ECV is influenced by exogenously defined market parameters, particularly the capacity payment price and the scarcity price (or price cap), as these parameters determine how reliability results are monetized within the proposed framework, reflecting its purpose: to assess the reliability contribution of VRE resources under current regulatory and market designs.

While the sensitivity analysis illustrates how variations in these parameters affect ECV, the scarcity pricing formulation is assumed fixed and externally defined. Alternative approaches, such as value-of-lost-load-based or endogenous scarcity pricing mechanisms, could alter the magnitude and distribution of ECVs, particularly in markets where scarcity prices are dynamic, as, for example, the case of the Electric Reliability Council of Texas (ERCOT), where scarcity prices are influenced from reserve shortages (Operating reserve demand curve, 2021). Extending the framework to incorporate alternative scarcity pricing formulations represents an opportunity for future research and would enhance its applicability to electricity markets with endogenous scarcity pricing.

The results of the sensitivity analysis indicate that the proposed methodology is compatible with policy measures that raise the capacity payment price and the scarcity price (or price cap), thereby improving reliability incentives for both conventional and VRE power plants.

3.4. Impact on the firm capacity of thermal generation

The methodology is used to determine the ECV of VRE. The existing mechanism can still be applied to traditional power plants to calculate their firm capacity. However, some adjustments are necessary for this mechanism. Since the VRE contribution to system reliability is now measured, it is reasonable to consider how peak-shifting should be addressed.

Fig. 8 shows the maximum system demand (3315.2 MW) during 2023 and the peak residual demand for the same period (3269.4 MW). During the peak hour, VRE contributes 45.9 MW, representing only 4.4% of its installed capacity. The residual peak demand coincided with the total system demand (Period 21 on 2023–10–12) due to the small contribution of VRE during this time. Therefore, the peak does not shift to another date or period.

Under the current mechanism, the total firm capacity of conventional generation must match the total maximum system demand, which is 3315.2 MW. However, since VRE's contribution to system reliability has been assessed, it is rational to consider peak-shifting (or the residual peak demand), a factor that many capacity value methods often overlook, according to (B. and Hobbs, 2017). Considering that the annual residual peak demand occurs on the same date and period, the firm capacity of conventional generation must be equal to this demand (3269.4 MW), to include the effect of the contribution of VRE. This implies that the firm capacity for thermal generation would be 45.9 MW lower under the proposed mechanism.

The firm capacity of conventional thermal generation decreases when the contribution of VRE generation to system reliability is considered. This means that thermal power plants will receive less capacity payments, which, if added to the expected reduction of their revenue from the energy market, due to the increase in VRE generation (Mills et al., 2020), may accelerate decommissioning and/or disincentivize investment in thermal power plants.

As Fig. 9 suggests that thermal power plants are the primary source of operational flexibility in the Dominican power system, so a mechanism that values this flexibility should be implemented to remunerate for this concept, being the Effective Ramping Capability (ERC) one possible method to quantify it (Lannoye et al., 2010), or by measuring

Fig. 7. /+ 25% PC scenarios.

Table 11
Breakdown of the definitive ECV for the -25% PC scenario.

Code	Initial - ECV [MW]	Additional ECV [MW]	Definitive ECV [MW]	Definitive ECV [%]
SOLPVNOR	0.0	1.1	1.1	0.8%
SOLPVSEA	0.0	3.2	3.2	1.8%
SOLPVSW	23.6	75.0	98.6	30.9%
WINDTNOR	12.0	69.2	81.2	40.6%
WINDTSWE	5.7	58.7	64.5	29.7%

the requirement for additional reserve capacity to maintain operational flexibility and remunerating it through another market mechanism. This may create a trade-off between lower capacity payments and a remuneration based on flexibility, which could prevent faster decommissioning of these power plants and/or reduce aversion to investment.

If operational flexibility is not valued appropriately, there will be little opportunity for more VRE integration.

Addressing this challenge requires a market design that incorporates robust capacity remuneration mechanisms, effective scarcity pricing signals, and well-structured ancillary service markets with specialized flexibility products (Milligan et al., 2016). As shown in the sensitivity analysis (3.3), raising both the capacity payment price (CMP) and the scarcity price or price cap (PC) can improve capacity payment and scarcity income for conventional thermal power plants, while also increasing the total income of VRE power plants.

3.5. Investment and policy implications of the proposed mechanism

The results indicate that the proposed methodology enables explicit quantification of the contributions of both solar and wind power plants to system reliability under scarcity or high demand, thereby enabling consistent assessment of their ECVs. In particular, the framework

Fig. 8. Residual peak demand on October 12th, 2023.

Fig. 9. The effect of VRE ECV on thermal power plants and operational flexibility.

identifies the technology–location combinations that maximize the ECV, which, for the analyzed case study, corresponds to wind power plants located in the northern region (WINDTNOR). These findings highlight the importance of considering both technological characteristics and spatial resource availability when assessing the adequacy of VRE.

The results further suggest that integrating energy storage systems (ESSs) can improve the ECV of VRE generation by allowing for the temporal shifting of energy production to hours with higher scarcity and reliability value (Byers and Botterud, 2020; Evaluation of impact, 2022). In regulatory environments where ESSs are not explicitly eligible for capacity payments, this mechanism may offer an indirect way to earn revenue through hybridization with VRE assets. For example, in 2023, solar PV plants in the southeastern and northern regions (SOLPVSEA and SOLPVNOR) show relatively low ECV, suggesting greater potential for ECV improvement through storage integration.

From a market design perspective, capacity payments based on the ECV may help mitigate investment gaps in VRE deployment by explicitly recognizing and monetizing their contribution to system reliability (Energy Systems Integration Group, 2023). By linking remuneration to ECV, the proposed approach can provide a more stable and predictable revenue component beyond energy market revenues. This aspect is particularly relevant in systems where energy prices are capped or scarcity prices are relatively low, as observed in the case study analyzed.

More broadly, the results reinforce the role of electricity market design in supporting the scale of VRE investment required to achieve decarbonization objectives (Hu et al., 2018; Algarvio et al., 2019). Without mechanisms that properly account for reliability contributions, VRE projects may face higher revenue uncertainty and greater investment risk. In this context, the proposed methodology can act as an analytical tool for policymakers by measuring how key market parameters, such as capacity payments, scarcity pricing, and energy offer structures, impact the revenue streams available to VRE assets through capacity remuneration mechanisms and scarcity rents.

Finally, although the methodology is directly applicable to electricity markets where capacity remuneration is in the form of capacity payments, such as those in Chile and Peru, its adaptation to alternative capacity market designs would require additional modeling considerations and is therefore beyond the scope of this study.

4. Conclusions and recommendations for future research

4.1. Key findings

This study developed and applied a methodology to quantify the ECV of VRE power plants, explicitly linking resource availability during scarcity or high demand with market-related conditions to assess their contribution to system reliability. The results demonstrate that ECV constitutes a conceptually distinct and complementary metric to traditional reliability indicators such as the ELCC or the FCE, as it captures how reliability contributions can be translated into economic signals through consideration of market design parameters, rather than only focusing on physical reliability.

Applying the methodology to the Dominican Republic's electricity market reveals that the capacity value, i.e. ECV, of VRE resources depends not only on their availability during scarcity but also on the interaction between market parameters such as scarcity pricing, capacity payment, and generation costs. The analysis emphasizes that current CRMs, which compensate only thermal and hydro generation, can be complemented with the proposed method, to recognize and remunerate the capacity value of VRE resources.

4.2. Limitations and future research

While the results provide relevant insights into the economic valuation of VRE reliability contributions, several limitations should be acknowledged. The proposed methodology is designed to determine an ex-post economic capacity value (ECV) for VRE resources that can be remunerated at the end of the year, alongside definitive capacity payments for hydro and thermal power plants, as in the case study. Consequently, it would benefit from future research that look to adapt the methodology to ex-ante scenarios, in which forecasted generation and demand profiles are used. This can be coupled with AI-based advanced forecasting and uncertainty modeling (Implementation of a multistage, 2024; Alblawi et al., 2022). In the same topic, forced outage rates are modeled explicitly only for thermal generation units, whereas the availability of VRE resources is represented using hourly generation data derived from real commercial metering. This approach is consistent with the ex-post nature of the case study, as the observed generation profiles capture the combined effects of resource variability, plant-level availability, inverter outages, and other operational disruptions that may have occurred during the study period. For ex-ante applications of

the proposed framework, the explicit modeling of VRE forced outage rates and availability becomes relevant and represents an opportunity for future research.

The ECVs obtained in this work are limited to the year in question, which reflects the system and market conditions observed in 2023, and must not be considered as a long-term reliability metric; therefore, these ECVs calculated represent the capacity value conditioned to the market parameters and VRE availability during scarcity periods for that year. Extending the analysis to multiple years would allow the understanding of the effect of inter-annual variability on the ECV and how this could influence long-term system planning from the policymaker's perspective. This is recognized as an important direction for future research.

Within the proposed Scarcity pricing is considered fixed and externally determined; thus, alternative methods of endogenous scarcity pricing could alter ECVs. Incorporating different scarcity pricing models into the framework offers a chance for future research and would improve its relevance to electricity markets with endogenous scarcity pricing, such as ERCOT.

At the time of the case study, utility-scale VRE penetration in the Dominican Republic stayed below 20%, leading to no VRE curtailment. As VRE deployment grows, curtailment is likely to become more common. Although some power systems exclude curtailment periods from capacity value calculations, the current methodology should assess whether curtailment must be considered or whether it should reflect potential incentives for investing in energy storage systems (ESSs) to improve the ECV. Future research could explore alternative approaches to curtailment and their effects at higher VRE penetration levels.

Furthermore, the allocation of capacity payment charges associated with VRE resources is not explicitly addressed in this study. While existing allocation rules based on peak demand could be applied, alternative schemes, such as allocation based on demand during scarcity hours, may be conceptually consistent with ECV's dependence on scarcity conditions. A systematic evaluation of such alternatives is left for future research.

Lastly, future research could extend this analysis by estimating the ECV at finer spatial resolutions, such as by technology and province rather than by region, or by evaluating plant-specific capacity values, as in (Mills et al., 2020), to enable benchmarking against the results of this study.

4.3. Concluding remarks

This study introduced an ECV framework to assess the contribution of VRE resources to system reliability under electricity market conditions. To further clarify the contribution of the proposed methodology, Table 12 provides a comparison between conventional capacity value approaches and the proposed ECV framework. The comparison highlights how ECV extends traditional reliability-based metrics by explicitly integrating market design parameters (i.e., capacity payments and scarcity pricing).

The comparative assessment in Table 12 clarifies the methodological advance of the ECV framework relative to established approaches. While traditional ELCC and capacity-factor-based methods quantify technical adequacy, ECV explicitly links reliability outcomes to market design parameters. By co-optimizing energy dispatch, capacity payments, and non-served energy, the framework captures how regulatory decisions translate physical availability into effective capacity value. As such, ECV complements existing reliability metrics by providing a market-based valuation of reliability contributions.

Applying the framework to the Dominican Republic electricity market shows that both solar photovoltaic and wind resources provide a meaningful contribution to system reliability, with ECVs that exceed their corresponding capacity factors in 2023. The results also demonstrate that ECV is sensitive to capacity payment prices and scarcity prices, confirming that capacity value may also represent an economic signal affected by market design. This finding is particularly relevant in

Table 12

Comparative assessment of capacity value methodologies and benefits of the proposed ECV approach.

Dimension	ELCC / FCE-based methods	Capacity factor / peak-hour approximations	Proposed ECV
Primary objective	Quantify technical contribution to system reliability	Approximate reliability using observed energy output	Quantify the economic contribution to system reliability
Link to market design	Not explicitly modeled	Not explicitly modeled	Explicitly integrates energy market rules and CRM design
Sensitivity to regulatory parameters	None	None	Directly captures CMP and price-cap/scarcity price effects
Treatment of VRE temporal alignment	Implicit	Simplified approximation	Explicitly values production during scarcity periods
Computational transparency	Moderate complexity	High simplicity	Moderate complexity
Applicability in emerging markets	Requires advanced probabilistic modelling and detailed data	Administratively simple, limited economic precision	Implementable using market data and parameters
Key contribution	Technical reliability assessment	Administrative simplicity	Links reliability assessment and market design

systems with administratively set price caps, where conventional scarcity signals may be insufficient to ensure resource adequacy.

Overall, the proposed ECV methodology offers a practical, policy-relevant tool to support the evolution of CRMs in power systems with increasing shares of VRE. While the numerical results are inherent to the case study, the conceptual framework can be generalized and adapted to other market designs, providing a foundation for future research on the interaction between reliability, market design, and decarbonization pathways.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Luis Hernández-Callejo: Supervision. **Miguel Aybar-Mejía:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Resources, Project administration, Funding acquisition. **René Báez-Santana:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Supervision, Software, Project administration, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Víctor Ocaña-Guevara:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision. **Máximo Domínguez-Garabitos:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Supervision. **Soares Joao:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision. **Bruno Henriques-Dias:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision.

Declaration of generative AI and AI-assisted technologies in the manuscript preparation process

During the preparation of this work the authors used Grammarly Pro in order to improve language, detect and correct grammatical errors, rephrase sentences, and check for plagiarism. After using this tool, the authors reviewed and edited the content as needed and take full responsibility for the content of the published article.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence

the work reported in this paper.

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Data availability

I have shared a link to my data at the Attach File step

Technical and economic data for energy market and capacity payment optimisation in the Dominican Republic's power market (Mendeley Data)

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